

Search For Potential Antitumour Compounds. Part I. Synthesis of Some Bis-(2-chloroethyl)-aminothiazoles

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Several nitrogen mustard derivatives of thiazole have been prepared with a view to testing their antitumour activity.

As nitrogen mustards, synthesised from aromatic, aliphatic, and heterocyclic amines, have been found to possess sufficient antitumour activity, further work on this class of compounds has been considered desirable. The most interesting product of aromatic mustard series, so far discovered, is *p*-(di-2-chloroethylamino)-(-)-phenylalanine¹, known as Melphalan. Activity of this compound is believed to be due to presence of bis-(2-chloroethyl)amino (or mustard) grouping and a carrier amino-acid side chain. Based on these observations, an isosteric compound, in which the benzene ring has been replaced by a heterocyclic ring, e.g. thiazolo, has been synthesised by the following route:

(I: R=H; R₁=CO₂Et).

(II: R=Ac; R₁=CO₂Et).

(III: R=Ac; R₁=CONHNH₂).

(IV: R=Ac; R₁=CONHNH₂SO₂Ph).

(VI: R=H; R₁=CONHNH₂).

hydrazide (IV) (10 g.) was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 170°. (Found: N, 13.0. $C_{17}H_{14}O_4N_4S_2$ requires N, 13.1%).

In a 500-ml r.b. flask, sulphonylhydrazide (IV) (10 g.) in ethylene glycol (50 ml) was heated with anhydrous potassium carbonate (10 g.) at 160° for 15 min. It was then diluted with hot water (100 ml). This solution was cooled and extracted with ether. On removal of the ether the aldehyde (V) (4 g.) was obtained as white crystals; m.p. 180-81°. (Found: N, 20.0. $C_3H_6ON_2S$ requires N, 19.8%).

Method (b).—2-Amino-4-methyl-5-ethoxycarbonylthiazole (I) (10 g.) was refluxed with hydrazine hydrate (10 g.) and ethanol (60 ml) for 3 hr., when the hydrazide (VI) separated (10 g.); m.p. 160-61°. (Found: N, 32.4. $C_5H_8ON_4S$ requires N, 32.6%).

A suspension (8 g.) of the hydrazide (VI) in water (120 ml) was added with stirring to a solution of potassium ferricyanide (16 g.) in ammonium hydroxide solution (sp. gr. 0.88, 100 ml). The mixture was stirred for about an hour. The crystals of thiazole aldehyde (V) separated (4 g), m.p. 180-81°. (Found: N, 19.6; $C_3H_6ON_2S$ requires N, 19.8%).

Azlactone (VII).—A mixture of the aldehyde (V) (6 g.), hippuric acid (85 g.), fused sodium acetate (4 g.), and acetic anhydride (13 g.) was heated to melting and then maintained at 100° for 2 hr. The mixture was cooled and diluted with water when the azlactone (VII) separated (8 g.). It was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 210°. (Found: N, 14.0. $C_{14}H_{11}O_2N_3S$ requires N, 14.1%).

Thiazole Acrylic Acid (VIII).—The azlactone (VII) (3 g.) was stirred with 0.2% NaOH solution (250 ml) at 100° for 45 min. It was then filtered and acidified with HCl. The acrylic acid (VIII) separating (2.8 g.) was recrystallised from acetone, m.p. 127°. (Found; N, 14.0. $C_{14}H_{13}O_3N_3S$ requires N, 13.9%).

Bis-(2'-hydroxyethyl) amino derivatives were prepared by addition of ethylene oxide (0.25M) to a solution of the appropriate amine or hydrazide (0.1 M) in acetic acid. The mixture was left overnight, made alkaline with $NaHCO_3$ and extracted with ethyl acetate. On removal of the ethyl acetate, the extract furnished the bis-(2'-hydroxyethyl)amino derivative. M.P., yield, and analysis of the derivatives obtained are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

R'.	R''.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
(HA)*	-CH=C-COOH					
	 NHCOPh	> 250°	40%	$C_{18}H_{21}O_5N_3S$	10.5	10.7
(HA)	-CO ₂ Et	> 250°	67	$C_{17}H_{18}O_4N_2S$	10.4	10.2
-NHCOMe	-CONH(HA)	216°	49	$C_{17}H_{16}O_4N_4S$	18.4	18.5
(HA)	-CONH(HA)	237°	72	$C_{19}H_{24}O_5N_4S$	14.4	14.8

* (HA) = -N(CH₂CH₂OH)₂

Mustard Derivatives.—The bis-(2'-hydroxyethyl)amino compounds (0.1M) were converted to the mustard derivatives by treating with thionyl chloride (0.25 M). The mixture was kept at 50-60° for about an hour and the excess of thionyl chloride was removed under reduced pressure. The mustard derivatives, so obtained, were recrystallised from benzene. The melting points, yield, and analysis of the mustard derivatives are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II*

R'.	R''.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
-M*	HNCOPh	100°	50%	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₃ Cl ₂ S	9.5	9.8
	-CH ₂ -C-COOH					
-M	-CO ₂ Et	237°	47	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₂ Cl ₂ S	0.1	9.0
NHCOMe	-CONHM	>250°	50	C ₁₁ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₂ S	16.5	16.6
-M	-CONHM	230-24°	63	C ₁₃ H ₂₀ ON ₄ Cl ₄ S	12.8	13.0

*The general structure is the same as in Table I

**M = -N(CH₂CH₂Cl)₂

2-Bis-(2'-Chloroethyl)amino-4-methyl-5-carboxythiazole (XI).—2-Bis-(2'-chloroethyl)-amino-4-methyl-5-ethoxycarbonylthiazole (1.5 g.) (Table II) obtained by the above method was hydrolysed by boiling it with HCl (conc., 20 ml) for 1 hr. The solution was then made less acidic by addition of sodium carbonate. The required *thiazole acid* (XI) precipitating was filtered and recrystallised from chloroform (0.9 g.), m.p. 196°. (Found: N, 9.7. C₉H₁₂O₂N₂Cl₂S requires N, 9.9%).

2-Amino-4-methyl-5-[NN-di-(2'-chloroethyl)] thiazole Hydrazide (XII).—2-Acetamido-4-methyl-5-[NN-di-(2'-chloroethyl)] thiazole hydrazide (1.5 g.) was boiled with HCl (1:1, 10 ml) for 30 min. and then basified with NaOH. The desired *aminothiazole* (XII) separating (1.0 g) was filtered and recrystallised from benzene, m.p. 130°. (Found: N, 19.6. C₉H₁₄ON₄Cl₂S requires N, 19.5%).

2-Bis-(2'-chloroethyl)amino-4-methyl-5-alanylthiazole.—The acrylic acid (IX) (2.5 g.) was mixed with red phosphorus (2.5 g.), acetic anhydride (14 ml), and HI (19 ml of 57%) and the mixture was well stirred and refluxed at 120° for 3 hr. The solution was filtered and the filtrate evaporated to dryness. The residue was dissolved in water and the solution was extracted with ether. The aqueous solution was evaporated to a syrup, treated with ammonium hydroxide, and evaporated. The residue was extracted with absolute ethanol and the ethanol-insoluble portion was recrystallised from benzene, furnishing the required *acid* (X) (1 g.) as white crystals, m.p. 179°. (Found: N, 12.6. C₁₁H₁₇O₂N₃Cl₂S requires N, 12.9%).

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